

The Prediction of Long Term Viscoelastic Properties of Fiber Reinforced Plastics

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ABSTRACT

A method for the experimental and analytical accelerated characterization of long term viscoelastic properties is presented. The time-temperature-stress superposition principle (TTSSP) is shown to serve as the basis for determining long term compliance data from short term creep test results. Nonlinear viscoelastic theories are discussed to provide the framework for the mathematically modeling of such a process. A time dependent Tsai-Hill-Zhurkov failure theory is used to determine long term failure properties from short term data. Compliance and failure data are incorporated in an incremental lamination theory to make long term laminate predictions. Comparisons are made between theory and experiment.

INTRODUCTION

Today's energy-oriented society tends to require light but strong structural materials operating at high stress levels for a prolonged time under possible hostile environmental conditions. Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) seem to be a perfect material because they are light, strong and can be tailored for a particular application. That is, they can be designed with the strong and stiff fibers in the directions of highest stress while the relatively weak and compliant polymeric matrix operates under low stress levels. However, the matrix is an important structural component as it serves to transfer the applied stress from fiber to fiber and from ply to ply. For this reason, the matrix, and hence matrix dominated properties, plays an important role in structural design and/or behavior of a composite material and cannot be ignored. Matrix dominated moduli and strength properties of polymer based composite laminates are time dependent or viscoelastic and are sensitive to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity. Because of this fact, the long term integrity of a composite structural component is an important consideration in the initial design process. Therefore, how viscoelastic matrix dominated modulus (compliance) and strength properties vary with time over the design life-time is necessary input to the initial design process. As many structural components are designed for years of service, property variations over years is often needed. Obviously, long term testing equivalent to the lifetime of a structure is impractical and undesirable. The alternative is to develop analytical and experimental accelerated characterization methods which can be successfully used for extrapolation.

This has been the principle research objective by the senior author and his associates for the last several years and also serves as the focus of the current paper.

The accelerated characterization plan described in the subsequent sections would give a manufacturer of polymer based composite structural components a method by which time dependent failures could be anticipated and avoided. Failures might be either the degradation of moduli with time, creep ruptures, matrix delaminations, ply separation, etc. The important feature is that only two compliance master curves need to be produced in addition to ordinarily or routinely performed stress-strain-failure properties. All necessary information could be produced in a very short time, perhaps a few days, and predictions on the order of years could be made.

ACCELERATED CHARACTERIZATION METHOD

The accelerated characterization procedure which was developed for polymer based composite laminates several years ago by Brinson [1] was initially based upon the well-known time-temperature-superposition principle (TTSP) for polymers and the widely used lamination theory for composite materials. More recently, however, a time-temperature-stress-superposition principle (TTSSP) has been utilized. Fundamentally, the idea is that certain environmental conditions such as temperature, stress, moisture, aging, etc. serve to accelerate the deformation processes associated with viscoelastic properties. At present only temperature and stress have been used as accelerating parameters to simplify testing procedures and data collection efforts.

The first step in the accelerated characterization method is the determination of lamina properties. These are determined using standard testing procedures for tensile specimen [2,3] as illustrated in Fig. 1. That is, tensile tests

Fig. 1a) Lamina Tensile Specimen and Coordinates; b) Stress-Strain Properties and Secant Modulus

for the fiber to load angles of 0° , 10° , and 90° are performed in a constant rate type test machine. Three stress-strain diagrams are produced as illustrated schematically in Fig. 1b. Each test would take on the order of five to twenty minutes each. A statistical sample of three to five specimens would be performed at each fiber angle. Each point on the stress-strain diagram as illustrated schematically in Fig. 1b by the secant modulus would be known. Thus, using the orthotropic transformation equation and an appropriate failure theory, the complete in-plane stress-strain response of a lamina from zero load to failure would be known for an arbitrary fiber angle. The variation of the secant modulus with fiber angle for short time (on the order of 10^0 per minute) including a scatter band is shown in Fig. 2a. Specific data of this type for a T300/934 graphite/epoxy (G/E) laminate is given in reference [3].

The information so obtained is normally used together with lamination theory or finite element procedures to find the static properties of a general laminate [2-4]. However, such a procedure is insufficient to determine long term (on the order of 10^6 - 10^8 minutes) design properties which are dominated by viscoelastic, (i.e., creep or relaxation) processes. The lamina time dependent property surface which is needed to predict long term design properties of a general laminate is shown in Fig. 2a. This surface can be produced using the

Fig. 2a Long Term Lamina Property Surface

Fig. 2b TTSSP for $[10^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$ Long Term Properties

aforementioned TTSSP method which is illustrated schematically in Fig. 2b. That is relaxation (creep) testing for 10° and 90° specimens can be performed at different temperature and stress levels for a short time (on the order of 10^1 - 10^2 minutes) and then shifted to form a modulus (compliance) master curve which would be valid over many decades of time. These master curves together with the orthotropic transformation equation and information on the time dependence of $[0^\circ]$ lamina is sufficient to produce the property surface shown in Fig. 2a.

In our work on T300/934 G/E laminates we have assumed the time dependence of $[0^\circ]$ lamina to be negligible. However, others have shown that fibers or $[0^\circ]$ lamina, including graphite, do have a time dependency which must be known for long time design situations [5,6].

The TTSSP methods described above have been amply documented for a T300/934 G/E material [7,8]. As indicated in Fig 2b, other parameters such as moisture, fatigue, aging, etc. could also be accommodated by the same kind of shifting procedures. While we have not as yet performed these types of analyses, a discussion of aging and moisture superposition can be found in reference [7]. See Crossman [5] for a discussion of a time-moisture-stress-superposition principle (TMSSP) method, and see Landel [9] for the property surface concept as applied to elastomers. The lamina property surface concept discussed above can be utilized with a variety of numerical procedures to determine the long term response of general laminates. Of course an analytical model of the property surface including failure is needed. A schematic of the complete accelerated characteri

Fig.3 Accelerated Characterization Method

For Laminated Composite Materials.

zation method to predict failures in general laminates is shown in Fig. 3. A brief discussion of the analytical procedures is given in the next section.

ANALYTICAL METHODOLOGY

The traditional manner by which long term properties are obtained from short term properties as shown in the block diagram of Fig. 3 is through graphical or semi-empirical curve fitting or extrapolation techniques. Of course, we would like to have a set of equations for the purpose of determining long term predictions from short term results based on rational continuum mechanics concepts if possible. These lamina analytical and delayed failure models to be discussed herein are described in greater depth in [10-13].

The stress-strain response of the $[10^\circ]$ and $[90^\circ]$ tensile specimens were nonlinear, particularly at the higher stress levels at which delayed failures

occurred. To account for this behavior, a nonlinear compliance model based on the Findley power law for creep was used [10,11, 14-16]. This relationship is of the form

$$\epsilon(t) = \epsilon_0 + m t^n \quad (1)$$

where $\epsilon_0 = \epsilon'_0 \sinh(\sigma/\sigma_\epsilon)$ and $m = m' \sinh(\sigma/\sigma_m)$

where n , ϵ'_0 , m' , and σ_m are material constants for a given temperature and moisture content. This uniaxial compliance model was generalized for biaxial creep loading of orthotropic materials as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_1(t) \\ \epsilon_2(t) \\ \gamma_{12}(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22}(t,\Sigma) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66}(t,\Sigma) \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where Σ represents the applied stress state and where $S_{22}(t,\Sigma)$ and $S_{66}(t,\Sigma)$ are obtained from $[90^\circ]$ and $[10^\circ]$ tests respectively.

To account for an interaction effect between the stresses, the octahedral shear stress in the matrix is used as the nonlinearizing parameter for the compliance predictions [10,11,17]. Both S_{22} and S_{66} then take on the form

$$S(t, \tau_{oct}^m) = 1/\tau_{oct}^m [\epsilon'_0 \sinh \tau_{oct}^m / \sigma_\epsilon + m' \sinh \tau_{oct}^m / \sigma_m (t^n)] \quad (3)$$

For general laminates under constant creep load conditions, the stress state in the individual plies will change with time because of the different creep rates in each ply. This process permits the load to be transferred from one ply to another. To account for this phenomena and to make the model applicable to a time varying creep load, a modified superposition principle was employed. Variations in the ply stresses due to load shifting or to changes in the applied mechanical load could then be systematically accounted for. The modified superposition principle for the Findley model was proposed by Findley and Lai [16] and was also given in [10,11]. This technique is equivalent to the Boltzmann Superposition Principle which is used for linear materials. Other models such as the Schapery single integral procedure may provide greater accuracy [17,18], and are currently being considered.

The failure model used was based on the assumption that the logarithm of the time to rupture varies linearly with the applied stress level

$$\log t_r = A + B\sigma \quad (4)$$

where t_r is the time to rupture, and A and B are material constants. Functional relationships for A and B in terms of temperature and other parameters may take on the form of the Zhurkov criterion [7,8,19]. To generalize this uniaxial form to account for a biaxial stress state in an orthotropic material, the Tsai-Hill failure criterion was modified to [10,11]

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X^2} - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{X^2} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{Y^2(t_r)} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S^2(t_r)} = 1 \quad (5)$$

The strength in the fiber direction, X , was assumed to be independent of time. The strength in the 90° direction, Y , and the shear strength, S , are functions

of the time to rupture. Again, to account for a time varying stress state in the plies, a linear cumulative damage rule was used [10,11,20].

The static short term properties of a general laminate may be obtained quite easily from lamina properties by lamination theory. DeRuntz and Crossman [21] have developed a numerical procedure based on the linear viscoelastic properties of a generalized Maxwell element and lamination theory. Crossman and Flaggs [5] have used the procedure to analyze time dependent warping of nonsymmetric laminates for hygrothermally induced strains. We elected to use a similar numerical lamination procedure except, in our case, the previously discussed Findley non-linear viscoelastic compliance model and the modified Tsai-Hill-Zhurkov failure criteria was used.

The computational scheme is based on obtaining successive stress, strain, and accumulated damage solutions as time is incremented. The strain state is determined at time $t + \Delta t$, based on the assumption that the stress state at time t is constant for the time step Δt . New ply stresses are determined at $t + \Delta t$ based on the current creep strains and the applied mechanical load. Accumulated damage is monitored until ply failure is predicted by the ply by ply failure criterion. The properties of "failed" plies are modified and the process continues until total laminate failure occurs. This approach is detailed more completely in references [10,22].

COMPARISONS OF EXPERIMENT AND PREDICTIONS

A testing program to elucidate and document all the many facets of the viscoelastic response discussed herein has been performed on a T300/934 G/E material. Only creep and creep recovery testing has been performed at various stress and temperature levels. Experimental procedures and results may be found in [3,4,7,10].

The ultimate test of the accelerated characterization method outlined in Fig. 3 is the comparison between long term predictions and test results. The

Fig. 4 Creep Rupture Data With Predictions For Laminate

method predicts compliance changes with time and creep ruptures for various temperatures or stress levels. However, only constant stress and temperature histories can at present be accounted for by analysis. As a result, all of our comparisons are for the latter condition. To avoid lengthy testing, all comparisons have been made for dry specimens at 320°F (160°C) which is below the glass transition of 380°F (193°C) for our T300/934 material. Predictions for one week were generated and compared with experimental results of the same duration. Comparisons between compliance predictions and results may be found in references [10,11]. Fig. 4 shows the comparisons between creep ruptures in a [90/45/-45/90] matrix dominated laminates. As may be observed predictions are quite conservative. Results for other laminates showed similar trends [10].

SUMMARY

The authors are encouraged by the results of the program to predict the nonlinear creep compliance and delayed failures in general laminated composites. The lamination theory assumptions on which the model is based has severe limitations and these are much more pronounced for the time dependent response than for an elastic analysis. Improvements are currently being contemplated. These are: The replacement of the Findley power law by a Schapery single integral model [18], the inclusion of interlaminar shear stresses in the lamination theory model and/or the use of a finite element method.

The failure model used is a modified elastic-plastic time independent approach to which we have arbitrarily added a time base. A more consistent continuum mechanics approach due to Crochet is being contemplated [23] along with other possible viscoplasticity models [24].

The authors feel that the described procedure is a viable approach to predicting the long term structural integrity of laminated composites. Of particular significance is the fact that these results are based on a minimal amount of short term tests on the unidirectional material.

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